

Holy Theological School of Halki

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Holy Theological School of Halki is located in Heybeliada, Istanbul. Until the 1970s was an active Greek Orthodox seminary, closed by the Turkish government. The school was built around a Byzantine monastery, Ayia Triada.

Date Range: 1844 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Heybeliada, Istanbul

Region tags: Byzantium, Balkans, Turkey

Heybeliada or in Greek "Halki" is one of the Prince's Island of Istanbul.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

The society in which the religious place is located is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Holy Trinity

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Saint Fotios

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Priests

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Tree, grove, or forest

↳ Type of elevation

- Hill

Notes: The Hill of Hope

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

- Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

- Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

- Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

- Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

- Yes

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- Yes

↳ Type of feature

- Terracing
- Trackway or road-surface

- Plantings
- Clearing
- Water feature
- Leveling of ground

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Stavridis, Vasileios, *Η Ιερά Θεολογική Σχολή της Χάλκης*, Athens 1988.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Illicit

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Reconstruction

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2023-2024

Has this place been looted:

– I don't know

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 3 Description: Official entry of the Ecumenical Patriarchate of Istanbul

- Source 1 Description: The official site of the seminary.
- Source 2 URL: <https://patriarchateofconstantinople.com/halki-theological-school.html#>
- Source 1 URL: <http://theologicalschoolhalki.com>
- Source 2 Description: Another official site
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.ec-patr.net/en/psaltai/chalki.htm>

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– Yes

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– Once

↳ In modernity
– Other (date-range):: Present day

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Communal

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:
– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Concrete etc.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 5000

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 70

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Lime

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No other.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Karamanli inscriptions on wells

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Frescoes

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Statues of Kemal Ataturk

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Teacher's portraits

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No other.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction,

etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– I don't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Iconography

Are there distinct features of the iconography:

– I don't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– I don't know

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Expensive tombstones are present

↳ Other

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Two on the same hill.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Two tombs of Greek Orthodox Patriarchs

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Supernatural Beings

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through a monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Nothing other.

Is a supreme high god present:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Do they have another type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Do they have kin relation with elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ other:

–Other [specify]: No other.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cult statue hidden:
 - No

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

- ↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
 - Yes

- ↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
 - Yes

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

- ↳ Other:
 - Other [specify]: No other.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes

- ↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: No other.

↳ Libations:

–Yes [specify]: Incense

↳ Offerings of food:

–Yes [specify]: Wine and Bread

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

–Yes [specify]: Cross and liturgical tools and objects

↳ Daily life objects:

–Yes [specify]: Glasses, plates, napkins

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 100

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Daily

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Wine

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Bloodless through the Divine Liturgy

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: Icons, oblations

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Institutions and Scriptures

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Spiritual services to the community (marriages etc.)

Religious Specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male specialists only

Bureaucracy

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– I don't know

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Holy Theological School of Halki, Théarvic, M.. "L'école Théologique De Halki". *Revue Des Études Byzantines* 8, no. 55 (1905): 353-61. <https://doi.org/10.3406/rebyz.1905.3643>.

Reference: Holy Theological School of Halki, Πετροπούλου, Ιωάννα. "Φιλίππου Αριστοβούλου Ανθολόγιο: Θεολογική Σχολή Χάλκης 1853-1856". *Δελτίο Κέντρου Μικρασιατικών Σπουδών* 5 (January 1, 1985): 187-239. <https://doi.org/10.12681/deltiokms.211>.